

INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Among the "world" languages, the role of the Russian language as a means of international communication is huge. Due to the entire direction of socio-political, economic, scientific– technical and cultural development of humanity in the 20th - 21st centuries, the Russian language is rightfully considered the world language. This is primarily explained by the "international" nature of modern science and the unprecedented pace of its development. Nowadays, it is important for every student to know the Russian language well. In this regard, it is important to use new methods of teaching the Russian language.

One of the demands placed on today's teachers is that they know well the methods applied to the educational process, which have passed the world's experience and are effective, and are able to apply them in practice. For this, it is necessary for the teacher to constantly search, learn and test what he has learned in the experiment, and he himself creatively changes and adds to these methods. Many educational methods are used in the organization of the educational process, among which interactive education and the interactive methods that form its basis are considered particularly effective. Below we will discuss some of the interactive methods used in teaching the Russian language. The words "interactive" and "interactivity" have the same meaning, and the word "interactive" is derived from the English words "inter" - "together" and "act" - "movement". Interactivity means being with something (for example, a computer) or someone (a teacher) in a co-moving or conversational mode. It follows that interactive education is, first of all, dialogic education, during which mutual cooperation between the teacher and the student, the student and the computer is carried out. As mentioned above, the basis of interactive education is conducting a lesson based on interactive methods. Interactive methods of education make it possible to use and activate the enormous educational power of students, to introduce elements of competition into the educational process: the mental strength of a group of learners is greater than the sum of the strength of its members (that is, the group the result is always greater than the sum of the individual results).

Methods of encouraging learning	Methods of understanding new material	Methods that allow you to think about what you have learned
Free writing. Cluster. Brainstorming. B-B-B drawing. A sequence of confused logical chains. Blitz survey.	Insert drawing. B-B-B drawing. Teaching guide. Teach each other. Ask each other. Two part diaries. The most basic concepts	The most basic concepts, repetition. T-chart. Classification table. What for? drawing. "What time?" diagram. Venn diagram. A five-minute essay. A ten-minute essay.

The methods of encouraging learning can be used in the teaching of almost all subjects taught in the general secondary education system. can be achieved. For this, the teacher himself must have an understanding of the application of the above methods. Methods such as free writing, cluster, brainstorming, B-B-B drawing, sequence of confused logical chains, Blitz-survey quickly attract students and increase their activity in the lesson. In Russian lessons, these methods should be used first in a simple form, and later in a more complex form, in accordance with the age of the students. Lessons organized using these methods are effective both in primary and upper grades. Methods of understanding new material are methods aimed at mutual cooperation of students in mastering science, learning by asking teachers and friends what they do not know and do not understand, and teaching others. These methods are considered to be effective not only intellectually, but also educationally, that is, these methods create feelings of friendship, honesty, kindness among students. The methods that allow students to think about what they have learned are methods that determine the extent to which students have mastered a new topic. By using them, students develop skills such as independent thinking and the ability to compare what they have learned. Designing and applying these methods in the educational process based on the purpose and content of the lesson leads to the following results:

- students' interest and motivation to study increases;
- learners are prevented from getting bored and tired in class;
- the learner develops creative work skills and active thinking
- helps to attract new associative thoughts and imagination freely and openly on the topic. In short, language learning is a complex process for students.

Students always face difficulties in learning foreign languages. The interactive methods that we listed above help to overcome these difficulties and serve to increase students' interest in learning foreign languages, especially Russian.

The subject of Russian language teaching methodology is quite broad and includes the following: necessary language material that must be mastered by students to acquire language skills; "feeding" the activity of the teacher aimed at choosing the necessary educational material and the methods of its implementation; the activity of the teacher in the organization of the educational process, which includes not only providing students with the necessary educational material, but also the implementation of diagnostic methods aimed at determining the level of knowledge and skills; activities of students aimed at mastering the necessary knowledge and skills, as well as developing skills within the studied subjects. In addition,

understanding the topic of Russian language teaching methodology is also an expected learning outcome. The methodology is aimed at studying the laws of formation of language concepts (knowledge), skills and qualifications in the field of the Russian language. It should be noted that, unlike pedagogy and didactics of psychology, the methodology studies not the general laws of teaching the Russian language, but specific things related to a certain language material.

The methodology considers the activity of the teacher and students as a process of interaction, expressed in joint activities, characterized by cooperation, while maintaining the leading role of the teacher. Thus, the method of teaching the Russian language is aimed at solving practical problems, including the development of effective teaching methods and methods. The purpose and tasks of the methodology The main purpose of teaching is to determine the place of science (Russian language) in the modern education system according to the methodology, to clarify its importance and necessity for the young generation. Within the methodology of teaching the Russian language, solving educational problems is carried out based on the selection of the most appropriate means. it is effective when used in the classroom system. In addition, the methodology takes into account the fixed number of classes in the academic year, the amount of educational material approved by the program and textbooks. The methodology involves the use of all tools and teaching methods, both special and general (textbook, notebook, blackboard, computer equipment, etc.). All of them are not used separately, but in a complex.

The technique is aimed at solving the following problems:

1. Why learn Russian - includes setting goals and objectives for learning.
2. What should be taught - reveals the content of teaching, the validity of the developed program, the use of specific textbooks and workbooks, manuals.
3. Teaching method - includes the development of teaching methods and methods, lesson structure and science cycle, educational equipment and educational tools.
4. Control of learning material learning - criteria for determining and evaluating the main methods of control.

According to the teaching methodology, the content of Russian language teaching includes:

1. Selection of a specific scientific concept by the teacher, which will be the basis of the entire educational process organized by him in the future.
2. Selection of sufficient and necessary terminological and conceptual apparatus.
3. To clearly define the range of knowledge, skills and qualifications that each student should acquire as a result of studying the subject.

It should also be noted that the teaching methods included in the teaching methodology are aimed not only at direct teaching, but also at the development of effective organizational means and forms of education. Currently, the Russian language teaching methodology is in close contact with psychology, philosophy, linguistics and pedagogy. Teaching the Russian language (and any subject in general) is a joint activity of the teacher and students. In order for the students to acquire the language thoroughly, the teacher should carry out certain educational (exercise) actions: explaining new material, giving assignments, asking questions and checking the correctness of the answers, etc. Students should also be active and perform a number of activities during the learning process: reading the text, learning words, doing exercises, answering the teacher's questions, etc. In traditional forms of education (in place), the actions of students are always determined and controlled by the teacher. It is he who decides what students should do, at what point, in what sequence, and for what purpose. And, of course, he

determines for himself what and how to do in the lesson (even outside the lesson). It directly teaches and teaches students to learn. But any teacher knows that the teacher's teaching action does not always produce the desired result. How to make the actions of the teacher most effective? It is necessary to explain to him what methods, techniques, methods to use, how to combine them with each other, how to behave in the audience to achieve the desired goal. In other words, we must teach him to consciously manage the learning process, including consciously organizing his learning activities so that the learning process gives us the best results. The topic of the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language is the educational process management system, i.e. a system aimed at the most effective mastering of the Russian language by students. The teacher cannot be hard-coded once and for all, but he can and should be taught to construct the educational process in such a way as to achieve the greatest effect in any specific situation. And for this, the teacher must know what to pay attention to, i.e. what factors determine the effectiveness of his actions; to be able to perform these actions correctly, competently.

Thus, the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language includes:

- 1) *factors determining the effectiveness of the educational process;*
- 2) *their systematic connection, i.e. how these factors are related to each other, which of them are primary, determining and which are secondary, act at any moment of learning and are related to certain conditions;*
- 3) *the rules by which the teacher should build educational activities.*

Teaching the Russian language, even in the absence of a language environment, is understood as teaching speech, communication and expression of thought in Russian. Thus, the methodology has a unique subject of study, which is not repeated in any discipline - teaching another language as a means of communication. This category defines the content of the entire educational process, the types of speech activities that must be mastered, and the levels of language knowledge that must be achieved in each of these types.

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